

CHILD
RESCUE

Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue

D4.4 ChildRescue Pilot Handbook, Release II

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is part of WP4 – “Missing Persons Cases Piloting and Evaluation” and provides an update of the final planning of Task 4.2 - “Pilots Planning and Preparation”.

The purpose of the deliverable is to update the final planning, coordination, set-up as well as the actual process of evaluation and validation of trial scenarios that will evaluate and validate the overall ChildRescue solution, as well as the ChildRescue concepts and tools.

More specifically, the deliverable aims to specify the pilot environment to be implemented for each participating end-user community. As described in the DoA, D4.4 constitutes the second and final release of the documentation of the set of trial scenarios that will run during each pilot (SoC, REDCROSS, Child Focus), including the actors involved, the evaluation indicators and the overall time-plan, as well as a fully operating prototype of the integrated platform for serving as the operation environment for the ChildRescue pilots’ implementation.

The pilot preparation activities focused also on the preparation of guidelines and documentation to support pilot partners in their end-user organisation (how to use the ChildRescue solution), producing the updated version of both the pilot guidelines and the end-user handbook. In addition, on the basis of this preparatory work, training seminars are organised targeting the actors/end-users in order to obtain the necessary know-how on using the ChildRescue solution during the pilot phase and after.

DISCLAIMER

This deliverable, D4.4 *ChildRescue Pilot Handbook, Release II*, was due on 31.3.2020 and it was prepared before the worldwide events that have followed the outbreak of COVID-19. For that, it includes the planning as decided among the partners before the COVID-19 outbreak. This planning cannot be realised according to the scheduled time-plan because of the preventive measures such as confinement taken by most countries, including the Project’s countries. By consequence, the plan for the second phase of the pilots (field exercises/real cases) is being constantly updated to mitigate the risks posed by the outbreak and to stay as close to the project’s goals and planning as possible.

Abbreviations

CM	Case manager
CPS	Crown Prosecution Service
EKKA	National Center for Social Solidarity (EKKA)
MFC	REDCROSS Multifunctional Center
PFA	Psychological First Aid
REDCROSS	Hellenic Red Cross
RFL	Restoring Family Links
SAR/ S&R	Search & Rescue
SoC	The Smile of the Child
SWD	Social Welfare Division
TS/RFL	Tracing/Restoring Family Links
UMC	Unaccompanied Migrant Children

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

ChildRescue project has the purpose to create a platform that facilitates the investigation of missing children and unaccompanied minors by using new technologies and promoting social awareness and involvement. D4.4 – “ChildRescue Pilot Handbook, Release II” constitutes the second (and final) release of the documentation of the set of trial scenarios that will run each pilot (updated version of D4.2 – “ChildRescue Pilot Handbook, Release I). To that end, D4.4 includes a detailed description about the main steps that should be followed when using the platform. More specifically, it presents the procedure followed by each involved actor when the platform is used by the pilot partners and it is supported by the technical partners. The pilot guidelines will be used to measure and guide the implementation of the ChildRescue platform during the piloting phase before initiating the real operation of the ChildRescue platform, a process that will prepare the execution of the real cases implementation.

In order to verify and confirm the accuracy and the precision of the pilot guidelines, two main steps were planned: to conduct a) simulation/tabletop exercise and b) field exercise (one by each of the three pilot partners). The simulation/tabletop exercises were conducted during the second semester of 2019 while the field exercises will be conducted during the first semester of 2020.

The precise results from the tabletop exercises are included in deliverable D4.3 “ChildRescue Pilot Experimentation Documentation Release I” and the documentation of the second pilot phase will be included in D4.5 – “ChildRescue Pilot Experimentation Documentation Release II” [M34].

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The structure of the deliverable is designed as follows:

- ↘ Chapter 1 includes the introduction of the deliverable, the purpose and the scope, the relation with other Work Packages of the project and the interconnection / relevance between them and finally the methodology followed for drafting this deliverable.
- ↘ Chapter 2 shows the main activities (i.e. simulation and field exercises and plan for real operation) that lead to the final pilot guidelines for the three pilot partners.
- ↘ Chapter 3 presents the performance indicators, which will be put to test when the platform is operational. To that end, the three pilot partners have updated the performance/validation indicators accordingly. In addition, it presents the evaluation plan for the pilots.
- ↘ Chapter 4 is the conclusion which summarises the main outputs of the previous chapters and describes forthcoming actions that will lead to the finalised version of the pilot guidelines.
- ↘ Chapter 5 is the Annex of the deliverable which includes the final End Users’ Handbook. This is the technical part that describes the role of each user and the way to use the platform.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

This deliverable 4.4 “ChildRescue Pilot Handbook, Release II” constitutes the second (and final) release of 4.2- “ChildRescue Pilot Handbook, Release I” that serves as a baseline for the other tasks of Work Package 4. WP4 is very important for the implementation of the Project since in this WP the consortium has the opportunity to - following all designs and planning made during the other WPs - test, explore, develop further and define the final version of the ChildRescue platform which is the actual objective of the Project. During the other WPs, the consortium has worked on the theoretical development of the ChildRescue platform in two levels a) the technical and b) the pilot organisations approach. Thus, WP4 offers the opportunity to utilise all the results of the other WPs and investigate, check and confirm the accuracy and originality in order to reach final conclusions that will lead to the final version of the ChildRescue platform which will be fully functional for all related partners.

Figure 1-1 Relation to other WPs and Tasks

The deliverable 4.4 – “ChildRescue Pilot Handbook, Release II” includes the main steps that were and will be followed during the simulation and field exercises respectively. The instructions and the main actions taken by the actors during the exercises will be reported and will constitute the principal guidelines of the real pilot exercise which is planned to run in 2020. At this stage, the aim is to finalise the steps which will be tested and updated three major times (i.e. simulation exercises, field exercises, real piloting) before the ChildRescue platform is fully functional and supportive to the pilot organisations.

In addition, the pilot organisations define the exact baseline of the performance indicators which will be used when the ChildRescue is used in the daily operations of the pilot organisations.

2 Pilot Guidelines

Pilot use cases are used to validate, demonstrate and evaluate the ChildRescue approach. ChildRescue introduces features that will enhance the standard processes of the organisations when handling such cases. The added value of ChildRescue to existing procedures will be assessed through the validation framework during the first and second pilot phase.

With the aim to create the pilot plans for the ChildRescue platform (that include the simulation and field exercises), it is an absolute need on behalf of the pilot organisations to be trained on the main steps they will follow when using the ChildRescue platform. Therefore, before the start of each pilot the technical partners conduct a training (face to face and/or via video call) with each pilot organisation including the main functionalities and steps that each actor should follow in order to use the ChildRescue platform and app. The content of the training seminar is mainly based on "Annex I: End Users' Handbook". It is a procedure that could be considered as a prerequisite in order to proceed with the actual implementation of the simulation and field exercises.

The ChildRescue pilot scheduling should be aligned with progress made in the development of the platform components and the integration of functionalities. Additionally, prior to the public release, the platform and application should be tested within closed user groups from the organisations. Thus, the ChildRescue pilot operation is divided into two phases: a) simulation/tabletop exercise and b) a field exercise respectively.

A tabletop exercise is one of the seven types of exercises identified by the Homeland Security Exercise Evaluation Program for preparing for disasters. These exercise types fall into two categories: **discussion-based or operations-based**. During the **tabletop exercise** (discussion-based) key personnel of the pilot organisations will have the opportunity to not only become more familiar with their own roles in the scenarios, but to see how the entire response will play out across the organisation. During the **field/full scale exercise** (operations-based) the participants will check and test their duties on-site, with multiple participants performing their duties in a simulated environment, imitating the response as closely to the real situation as possible.

Two use cases are explored in the ChildRescue demonstrators and supported by the pilot organisations.

Missing Child Emergency Case: This scenario involves a standard case where a child goes missing from home, the incident is reported to the hotline, a decision for publication of a public appeal is taken, the community and search parties become engaged, and the child is located and returned to his family.

Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors: The participation of REDCROSS in ChildRescue focuses on the discovery and identification of Unaccompanied Migrant Children (UMC).

The specific pilot planning for each of the organisations is presented in the following sections.

2.1 Pilot Plan in Greece for missing children

2.1.1 Changes from 1st iteration

The only change that has occurred compared to the initial planning is the movement of the internal testing to a larger controlled group of case managers and volunteers (100 people) from the second semester of 2019 to the first semester of 2020, since it was agreed that this phase is more logical to be accomplished after the field exercise and before the real cases implementation.

In addition, this internal testing had to be replaced by a second tabletop exercise that was organised in order to test the volunteers' app that was not tested during the first tabletop exercise.

Below the updated and final pilot plan in Greece for missing children by SoC is presented as well as the plan for the piloting of real cases.

Pilot plan

The pilot plan for missing children in Greece by SoC consists of two main phases. The first phase for SoC consists of two sub-phases: sub-phase I.1, internal testing and 1st tabletop exercise (with the involvement of 10-20 people) and sub-phase I.2, 2nd tabletop exercise. During the first sub-phase, the first release of the platform/mobile app was tested, which did not include the volunteer app while during the second sub-phase the volunteer app was tested. The second phase consists also of two main phases: sub-phase II.1, performing a field exercise where the second release of the platform/app will be tested, including the functionalities for volunteers. After the field exercise an internal testing with a controlled group of about 100 people will be conducted (sub-phase II.2), where the users will be familiarised with the data entry and handling of the platform and the app before citizens will start downloading it.

Specifically, the time-plan and the steps that were and will be followed for the piloting in Greece is:

- [M18] - June 2019: Operation of the first release of the mobile app
- [M19-21] - July – September 2019: Internal testing of the first release of the mobile app and provision of comments to the technical partners
- [M22] - October 2019: Training and simulation/tabletop exercise (one day) on the basis of the developed scenario– testing was conducted in a controlled group of 16 people (the testing included registered and unregistered users and the key actors of the pilot organisation –Case Managers, Network Manager, etc. - as well as the technical partners) (sub-phase I.1)
- [M22-23] - October – November 2019: Modifications to the platform/app by the technical partners
- [M24] – December 2019: Training and 2ndsimulation/tabletop exercise (one day) on the basis of the developed scenario – testing of the volunteers app was conducted in a controlled group of 17 people (the testing included registered and unregistered users and the key actors of the pilot organisation –Case Managers, Network Manager, Volunteers etc- as well as the technical partners) (sub-phase I.2)
- [M25-26] - January – February 2020: Modifications to the platform/app by the technical partners
- [M27] –March 2020: Training (one session) and field exercise (second session) of the full version of the ChildRescue platform/mobile app and the volunteers' app (sub-phase II.1)
- [M28] - April 2020: Final version of the platform/mobile app

- [M27-28] – March – April 2020: Testing to a larger controlled group of volunteers (e.g. 100 people) (sub-phase II.2) – data entry and internal handling of the platform
- [M29] - May 2020: Public release of the ChildRescue platform/mobile app

2.1.2 Simulation/tabletop exercise

The 1st simulation/tabletop exercise was conducted in October 2019 at the premises of the Organisation “The Smile of the Child” during which the personnel of the Organisation and the technical partners (UBITECH, SLG, S5), along with the coordinator, NTUA, participated for the support of this exercise.

The training of the different actors/users was conducted simultaneously with the simulation/tabletop exercise on the basis of the scenario below.

Pilot Scenario

A 16-years old girl, Maria, participates in the five-day school trip to Athens (Lyceum of Argostoli, Kefalonia Island). The school`s hotel is in Palaio Faliro. Every day, the school visited a different place of interest. For Maria, it is the first time to be in the capital city, Athens.

The day that Maria disappeared, the school had visited Acropolis. Then, all together they went for lunch and afterwards they had a free time. Everyone had to be back at 17h00 in order to leave for the hotel. The responsible professor then discovered that Maria was not there. Her friends sitting next to her said that Maria went to the toilet around 16h00. On her seat, her jacket, a backpack and her mobile phone were found. After a quick search of the area, the professor informed Maria’s parents and then the Police Station about the missing child. At 18h15, the police officer reported the missing child and formally informed the parents of the girl. The Police Station activated its forces in the area. However, it was 19h00 and the weather was becoming bad with high winds and heavy rain, while temperature was below 15°C. The rest of the schoolmates were in the bus waiting for any progress.

At 19h30, the responsible teacher returned in the tavern in case Maria would come back and at the same time communicated with the European Hotline for Missing Children 116000 of the Organisation “The Smile of the Child” asking for advice and guidance.

The Social Worker of the European Hotline for Missing Children 116000 (organisation Case Manager) recorded all the information provided by the responsible professor and then he/she communicated with the parents from whom he/she learned that Maria used to receive negative comments and teasing from her classmates because of her appearance and her mother’s origin, too. The parents were terrified because the last days Maria had expressed her intention to skip/escape from this situation while her parents insisted in participating in the school excursion. The parents added that Maria had regular sessions with a psychologist, and she followed an antidepressant treatment.

It is 20h00 and the research of the Police Motorcycle Unit (DI.AS) has no results yet and the Division of Missing Persons of the Hellenic Police and the responsible Prosecutor accept the proposal from the organisation “The Smile of the Child” to activate the Amber Alert Hellas.

Maria’s parents agree and follow the procedures foreseen during this process. At 20h25, the Amber Alert is activated.

Until now, the procedures followed are those that are foreseen for every new case occurred in the Operational Emergency Centre of “The Smile of the Child”.

At this stage, new procedures are introduced due to the ChildRescue platform, where each responsible actor is reacting complementarily/ supplementary through the platform.

The actors /participants were:

- Visitor (Anonymous user): 1 person
- Simple User (Registered user): 2 persons
- Search & Rescue Team Member: 1 person
- Volunteer Team Member: 1 person
- Organisation Case Manager: 1 person
- Organisation Network Manager: 1 person
- Organisation Coordinator Manager: 1 person
- Organisation Owner: 1 person

Presence, support and training by representatives of the technical partners was also foreseen.

New procedures

The Organisation Case Manager enters the case's information in ChildRescue. An Alert is sent to the users in the area that is defined by a centre and a dynamically changing radius for a duration of 24 hours. The Organisation Coordinator Manager has access to the data.

Three users (two registered and one anonymous), provide feedback via the app.

- 20h40: User A uploads a photo outside the Acropolis Museum with a girl that looks like Maria, but with black shoes and a backpack.
- 20h41: User B texts a message mentioning that Maria was at Monastiraki Station getting on the train with direction to Kifissia. "The girl that you are searching for is inside the train going towards Kifissia. I am not sure if she disembarked at Herakleion station or if she continued. I disembarked at OAKA."
- 20h43: User C texts a message referring that Maria was in a clothing store in The Mall Athens.

"I have the impression that the girl that you are searching for is at Marousi Mall and if I am not mistaken, I saw her inside the X store a few minutes before. I am working here as a cashier and she was waiting in order to pay."

The Case Manager evaluates the feedback and informs Police and in parallel examines the social media and the potential routes. In parallel, the Case Managers feed the system with other information that they receive from citizens or relatives via the 116000 Hotline.

- 21h10: User D sends to the app text informing that from 16.00 – 18.00 outside the Thision station, Maria asked for information about how to go at Piraeus. "I saw Maria at Thision station definitely after 4.30 and before 5.30. She asked me how she can go to Piraeus and I told her to take Line 1 but I think that she did not understand. She was not OK... She asked me for a ticket, but I did not have and I gave her 1 euro; this was what I all had in coins".
- 21h30: User E uploads a photo from Metro station of Ilioupoli, with a girl that resembles with Maria. The user writes: "I am security at Metro station of Ilioupoli. If Maria is the person in the photo, then she is nearby the metro lines and she is not getting in any of the passing trains. I asked her if she needs help, but she did not respond and got away from me".

Based on the received evidence, the location area where the alerts are sent is widened, because most probably Maria is not at Acropolis area. Soon, the provided evidence indicates automatically a specific area.

The Network Manager mobilises the Search and Rescue Team for Missing Children "Thanassis Makris" of the Operational Emergency Center of "The Smile of the Child" that was already in readiness (via the Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Leader) since 12 rescuers and 2 Canine Teams were already on alert (maximum activation time: one hour). The Network Manager coordinates and provides guidance to the operational teams via the app (not conducted in practice because the volunteer app/platform was not ready – was tested in December 2019 and will be fully tested during the field exercise).

However, a citizen calls at the hotline 116000 and indicates that he saw Maria at the culture centre of Niarchos.

The Network Manager evaluates the evidence. Via the exercise, it was made clear to the participants that until locating the missing child, no area can be excluded from the search.

When Maria is found, the Case Manager, coordinator and owner perform their duties (e.g. closing case, archiving case, case report, notification of app users that the missing person was found, removal of photos etc.).

During the **2nd simulation/tabletop exercise**, the same scenario was used in order to test the volunteers app. During the exercise the users (simple and registered users, case manager, coordinator manager, network manager, volunteers, team leaders) tested the platform and the app and provided feedback.

A full test of alerts, invitations, notifications, facts, volunteers, files, places, locations, maps and control features of the platform and collaboration space was accomplished. Thus, on the basis of the aforementioned scenario, the steps included:

- Data entry by the case manager in order to create the alert
- Registration of volunteers
- Invitation of volunteers to participate and receipt of response and appointment of the team leader(s)
- Provision of facts by the users
- Evaluation of the facts by the case manager
- Overview of the process by the organisation coordinator
- Coordination of the search process by the network manager (check of points of interest on the map, communication with the team leader for provision of directions to the search and rescue team)
- Provision of feedback to the technical partners.

The actors /participants were:

- Visitor (Anonymous user) & simple user (Registered user): 2 persons
- Volunteer Team Member/Leader: 5 persons
- Organisation Case Manager: 1 person
- Organisation Network Manager: 1 person
- Organisation Coordinator Manager: 1 person

Presence, support and training by representatives of the technical partners was also foreseen.

2.1.3 Full scale / Field exercise

The full-scale exercise includes all the components of a functional exercise and adds the actual responding field units. It is intended to test and evaluate the operational capability of the emergency management system in an interactive manner. For the purposes of the project, the aim is to test the ChildRescue platform and app.

The field exercise is planned to be conducted at the end of March/beginning of April 2020.

Prior to the exercise the actors will get familiarised and trained on the use of the platform and app. In addition, the necessary actors will be registered (e.g. registration of volunteers).

Setting of the exercise: The exercise will be held at the premises of “The Smile of the Child”. Most of the actors will be in one room while the users and volunteers will be elsewhere.

The scenario that will be used will be the same that was used for the simulation/tabletop exercises. For the purposes of the exercise unknown facts (injects) will be introduced during the exercise. Each inject is designed to elicit a specific response from participants, such as triggering an action or response decision that is in line with the pilot plan. Participants can also be tested on their ability to prioritise tasks during a case and to identify non-critical events that can be set aside. Injects will be released at timed intervals. They can be given either by the facilitator or a role player, who will deliver the injects to participants. The way that injects are delivered to participants has a significant impact on the realism of the exercise – organisers will be as creative as imagination and resources allow. Injects can be delivered in any form and by any method of communication. For example, an inject could be a situation report from the field, a television or radio broadcast, a phone call or an email; or it could be something delivered in person by a role player or facilitator acting out a role. Designing realistic delivery methods can help to create a more interesting and engaging exercise for both the participants and the exercise management team.

Figure 2-1 – Actors and places of the field exercise at SoC

On a preparatory level, The Smile of the Child will inform the citizens in the nearby area that an exercise is in progress in order not to be alerted (e.g. by the search dogs).

The different roles assigned during the exercise will be:

Lead facilitator / exercise manager: The Lead Facilitator will serve the traditional role of an exercise controller and will have several key responsibilities during the exercise.

First, the Lead Facilitator will assign roles to exercise staff and brief them on the details of the exercise. Second, the Lead Facilitator will lead and guide the exercise by presenting information to the exercise participants. The different actors will follow the Lead Facilitator Guidelines to keep the exercise moving forward. He will provide messages to the exercise participants to ensure key decision points in the exercise are reached. Third, the Lead Facilitator will observe and coach. In this role, he will observe the actions of exercise participants and be on the alert for potential unexpected issues. The Lead Facilitator may also intervene to help the team members clarify their decision making by asking questions about their thought process and the factors they considered in making choices.

Finally, the Lead Facilitator will wrap up the exercise, overseeing clean-up and ensuring that all players and volunteers are accounted for.

Evaluator: The primary responsibility of the Evaluator is to assess the exercise and get feedback by the participants related to the ChildRescue platform/app. The Evaluator will have passive role and will not interfere with the exercise, unless he/she is also playing the role of Facilitator.

Missing child / actor: the role of missing person of the exercise will be undertaken by one observer.

Case manager: the case manager / 116000 hotline operator will be responsible for entering in the platform of the missing case's data. The participation of the rest of actors starts after the completion of this process by the case manager. In addition, the case manager will be responsible for receiving and evaluating facts by the users.

Network manager: the network manager will monitor the data provided by the case manager and the facts and will coordinate the search and rescue mission via communication with the appointed team leader.

Search & Rescue / Volunteers: the search & rescue volunteer team members will use the volunteer app in order to respond to the request to participate or not in the investigation, will be activated, will communicate and provide feedback to the search & rescue / volunteer **team leader** and network manager.

Users (anonymous users, registered users): will share via the app information regarding the potential route and/or the profile of the missing child.

In addition, the roles of **Organisation Coordinator Manager** and **Organisation Owner** will be tested.

At the end of the exercise, a debriefing will be held, as well as the evaluation.

A full test of data entry, alerts, facts, volunteers, files, places and control features will be performed, namely:

- Data entry by the case manager in order to create the alert
- Invitation of volunteers to participate and receipt of response and appointment of the team leader(s)
- Provision of facts by the users
- Evaluation of the facts by the case manager
- Overview of the process by the organisation coordinator
- Coordination of the search process by the network manager (check of points of interest on the map, communication with the team leader for provision of directions to the search and rescue team)

- Final outcome of the exercise
- Closure and archiving of the case
- Provision of feedback to the technical partners.

For the realisation of the exercise SoC will ensure the following tasks:

- administration and logistics (e.g. participants, materials, venues, facilities, technology and connectivity);
- site visits to proposed exercises venues;
- development of scenarios, injects and exercise material;
- evaluation planning;
- briefing and training (e.g. of evaluators, facilitators, role players and participants);
- preparation of debriefing and exercise report;
- communications and media; and
- safety and security.

2.1.4 Real cases

After the aforementioned exercise, about 100 volunteers and case managers from different areas of Greece will be trained on the use of the platform and the app and will start encoding data from real cases in order to get familiar with the new procedure, before communicating with the general public.

The number of registered cases will be minimum 3. This process will be held during April and May 2020 before the public release of the app.

Upon public release of the app, the ChildRescue app and platform will be in full use for at least 4 active and running real cases that the Hotline 116000 will handle. The new procedures will run in parallel with the existing ones. The provisioned number of citizens' contribution is 35; however, the number of information that the 116000 hotline receives depends on the characteristics of a specific case (e.g. there are cases where the citizen's contribution is quite limited for different reasons). Therefore, if necessary, the number of cases where the platform/app will be used will be increased.

In order to ensure a smooth operation, SoC will inform all of its collaborators and partners.

During the process of real cases piloting the validation framework will be followed.

The pilot with real cases will ensure piloting with three categories of missing children:

- runaways
- lost, injured or otherwise missing children
- missing unaccompanied migrant minors

Piloting with abductions cannot be ensured since the number of abductions in Greece is very low and SoC cannot ensure that such cases will be available in order to be tested.

During this phase, the process will be closely monitored and supervised in order to identify any potential issues that need to be addressed for the full operation. Actions taken will be documented.

This phase will include all the following actors:

- Visitor (Anonymous user)
- Simple User (Registered user)
- Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Member
- Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Leader

- Organisation Case Manager
- Organisation Network Manager
- Organisation Coordinator Manager
- Organisation Owner
- ChildRescue Administrator

During this phase the following infrastructure will be utilised:

- The European Hotline for Missing Children 116000 (interconnected with the 112 European Emergency Number) and staff of the Emergency Response Coordination Center of the organisation (line operators, psychologists, social workers)
- The mobile command centre of the organisation
- The 'Thanasis Makris' Search and Rescue Team (handlers and dogs) who have received specialised training and Certification by NSARDA
- Rescue Vehicles and radio networks
- Mobile Medical Units of Intensive Care for Children and Newborns (if needed)

2.2 Pilot Plan in Belgium for missing children (Child Focus)

2.2.1 Changes from 1st iteration

Compared to the initial pilot planning, the plenary partner meeting in Athens in January 2020 decided to slightly delay the second pilot with one month in order to better fit the development process of the application. Therefore, the field exercise of the beta version that will include also the volunteers' app will be executed in the end of March / beginning of April.

Below it is presented the updated and final pilot plan in Belgium for missing children by Child Focus as well as the plan for the piloting of real cases.

Pilot Plan

The pilot plan for missing children in Belgium consists of two main parts: the first and the second part. The 1st pilot consists of two phases: Phase I, internal testing and tabletop exercise (with the involvement of 18 people) and Phase II, internal testing to a controlled group. During the 1st pilot, the 1st version of the platform/mobile app will be tested, that will not include the volunteer app. The 2nd pilot consists of performing a field exercise where the 2nd version of the platform/app will be tested, including the functionalities for volunteers and geo-localisation.

Specifically, the time-plan and the steps that will be followed for the piloting in Belgium is:

- September 2019: Training on the functionalities of the platform for the employees involved in Phase I and II
- October 2019: simulation/tabletop exercise (one day) on the basis of the scenario below – testing will be conducted in a controlled group of 18 people (Phase I)
- January 2020: training on updated platform (if modifications were needed after Phase I)
- March 2020: Field exercise of the beta version that will include also the volunteers' app

- April 2020: Final version of the platform/mobile app
- May 2020: Public release of the ChildRescue platform

2.2.2 Simulation/tabletop exercise

The 1st simulation/tabletop exercise was conducted on 21st of October 2019 at the Child Focus-premises and was attended by 10 staff members of the operational department of Child Focus and with the support of the technical partners (UBITECH, SLG, S5), along with the coordinator, NTUA, through Skype.

The initially foreseen scenario was used during this exercise:

Pilot scenario

Officer De Boeck from the Police Zone Wemmel calls the 116000. Our receptionist, An, receives a call from the officer upon request from the CPS (The Crown Prosecution Service). The officer mentions that Laura, 14 years old (date of birth 15/09/2005), has been missing since this morning. She was supposedly on her way to school, but never arrived.

She had the following things with her:

- her cell phone – but it is disconnected
- her school bag – but she carried nothing unusual with her (nothing seems missing from her room)
- bank account empty – some cash but total amount unknown
- we are not sure whether she has a pass for public transport. She recently lost it and had to apply for a new one

Together with the officer, An establishes a first profile of Laura:

- Psychological problems
- No medication
- It is unusual for her to disappear without a trace
- She never stayed out longer than permitted
- She never skipped classes
- Social media account inactive during last couple of weeks
- Boyfriend unknown

The officer gives the contact details of the parents. The parents live together.

At 3.30 p.m. the receptionist transfers information orally and via the CRM-system to the case manager on duty. The case manager creates a casefile in the CRM-system and contacts the police officer. We get more details on what happened to Laura. She left at 7 a.m. to school, not showing any suspicious behaviour. She took her school bag with her. It didn't look like she was carrying more weight than on other days. There was no particular fight the day before. She left, but never arrived at school in Jette, a couple of stops away. She left in the direction of the bus stop. Laura is officially reported as missing and the neighbourhood examination as well as the examination of her cell phone and camera images

were negative. We also obtain some more profile clarifications. These last couple of days the parents have noticed some behavioural changes. She has been extremely introvert, hiding in her room and struggling with negative thoughts. Her school performance has deteriorated the last couple of weeks. The school council mentions that she has been very distracted. There have not been any suicide-attempts in the past.

Because of lack of results, the CPS requests diffusion via ChildRescue App. The Federal Office for Missing People has been informed.

At 4 p.m., the case manager calls the parents. She informs them about the involvement of Child Focus and checks whether the parents have sufficient emotional support. The Case manager requests a recent photograph (to be send via mail foto@childfocus.org) and checks the description of the missing girl. The parents are informed about possible media attention and the possibility of deflecting press to the central communication department in Child Focus. Together they evaluate the impact of a public appeal and the parents approve the diffusion via ChildRescue App.

We also obtain extra clarifications but little more is known. Laura has lived quite isolated in her room for the last two weeks. The parents are in touch with Laura's best friends – they are very worried too. Her friends mention the possibility that she might have a boyfriend, but they don't know a lot about him, except that he is a lot older than Laura.

We discuss Laura's hang out spots. She likes to hang out in parks (park next to the Atomium near the movie theatre) and often meets up with friends on place de Mirroir in Jette. When she goes to the city centre, she hangs around Place Saint-Catherine. These last weeks she declined to meet up with friends.

At 4.30 p.m., the Case Manager calls the Federal Office for Missing People. The officer on duty is aware of the diffusion and might follow-up with a press release in the evening news of 7 p.m. Besides the diffusion via ChildRescue, we consider the idea of hanging out posters in her neighbourhood – as last point seen. The officer will bring this idea to the attention of the CPS. The CPS approves. The case manager informs the back-up (Organisation Coordinator Manager) and gives input in the ChildRescue app, targeting a 10 km radius around the neighbourhood (Wemmel): Laeken, Jette and city centre Brussels (1000 Brussels).

A total of 16 testimonies (4 anonymous, 12 registered) come in half an hour through the ChildRescue App. The testimonies are opened by receptionist who copies their content into the CRM file and on e-mail or fax to share with the police. Based on the received evidence, the location where the alerts are sent is widened and extended to the whole Brussels area because there is indication that Laura might be at the other side of the city. Soon, the provided evidence indicates automatically a specific area. Another 2 testimonies (1anonymous, 1 registered) are received through ChildRescue and shared with the police.

The Case manager gets a report from the police, that based on one of the testimonies, Laura has been in Jette. The case manager closes the case in ChildRescue, and followers are alerted that Laura has been located safe and sound.

2.2.3 Field exercise

The full-scale exercise includes all the components of a functional exercise. During the exercise the functionalities related to the volunteers as well as the predictive analytics and the geo-localisation will be tested, which was not the case for the first pilot phase.

The field exercise is planned to be conducted at the end of March/beginning of April 2020. Prior to the exercise, the Child Focus staff working with the volunteers (who are different from the ones in the operational department which have been involved in the first pilot and will be off course also involved in the second) will get familiarised and will be trained on the use of the platform and app. In addition, the necessary actors will be registered (e.g. registration of volunteers).

The exercise will be organised at the Child Focus offices, but as it will also test the geo-localisation aspect of the app and the usability for the volunteers, several people will also be outside of the offices, throughout Brussels.

Steps

During the field exercise the aforementioned steps of the simulation/tabletop exercise will be repeated and the following steps will be added in order to test all functionalities of the 2nd version of the ChildRescue Platform.

Posters

Case manager contacts the 3 colleagues responsible for producing (responsible 'Group 1'), printing (responsible 'Group 2') and diffusing the posters (responsible 'Group 3' aka Network Coordinator).

The responsible group 1 also disseminates the poster via the ChildRescue App. Target area is identified with the case manager.

The Network manager is notified in order to establish a team of 8 volunteers. They will physically go out to test the functionalities of the ChildRescue app, so they will be at 8 different locations to receive the task list via ChildRescue and report back through it. The Network responsible sends through ChildRescue the checklist to volunteers in the area. 8 volunteers report back information about posterage through ChildRescue: where did they put out posters?

In parallel, the case manager retrieves information from similar past cases and from the profiling features of the system. The case manager evaluates the feedback and at the same time examines the social media analysis and possible routes. The provided evidence indicates automatically a specific area.

When Laura is found, the case manager closes the case in ChildRescue. Followers are alerted that Laura has been located safe and sound and also the volunteers are automatically alerted that they have to go out and take down the paper posters. The Network responsible sends out a checklist to the relevant volunteers in the area through ChildRescue. 8 volunteers report back via ChildRescue on having taken down the posters. The file is fully closed and archived in ChildRescue.

During the field exercise, the organisation's **infrastructure** will be deployed and specifically:

- The European Hotline for Missing Children 116000. The field exercise will be done at a normal workday so as to also fully test the compatibility with existing procedures and dealing with several cases at the same time.
- The team of volunteers

2.2.4 Real cases

Description of the pilot phase with real cases (time-plan, actors, cases, trainings, etc)

Upon public release of the app, the ChildRescue app and platform will be in full use for at least 4 active and running real cases that the Hotline 116000 will handle. It has to be noted that the decision of the launch of a public appeal is always taken in concertation with our law enforcement partners and therefore is not in the full control of Child Focus.

The new procedures will run in parallel with the existing ones. The provisioned number of citizens' contribution is 35; however, the number of information that the 116000 hotline receives depends on the characteristics of a specific case (e.g. there are cases where the citizen's contribution is quite limited for different reasons).

In order to ensure a smooth operation, Child Focus will inform all of its collaborators and partners, mainly the Federal Police and the Federal Prosecutors Office.

During the process of real cases piloting the validation framework will be followed.

The pilot with real cases will ensure piloting with three categories of missing children:

- runaways
- lost, injured or otherwise missing children
- missing unaccompanied migrant minors

Piloting with abductions cannot be ensured since the number of abductions in Belgium is too low and Child Focus cannot ensure that such cases will be available in order to be tested.

During this phase, the process will be closely monitored and supervised in order to identify any potential issues that need to be addressed for the full operation. Actions taken and possible recommendations will be documented.

This phase will include all the following actors:

- Visitor (Anonymous user)
- Simple User (Registered user)
- Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Member
- Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Leader
- Organisation Case Manager
- Organisation Network Manager
- Organisation Coordinator Manager
- Organisation Owner
- ChildRescue Administrator

During this phase the infrastructure of Child Focus and its European Hotline for Missing Children 116000 will be utilised as well as our network of volunteers.

2.3 Pilot Plan in Greece for unaccompanied children

2.3.1 Changes from 1st iteration

There is only a slight, yet important, deviation from initial planning as far as the second pilot is concerned, due to the need to fit and be implemented properly as soon as the application is ready for use. Thus, 2nd pilot was postponed to April. According to the new timeframe (due to the reason mentioned above), it is foreseen that the next pilot (simulation exercise) is to be done most probably mid or at the latest end of April (Easter vacations as well as internal organisation's issues do not allow for earlier implementation). The change of plans has been discussed during the plenary meeting in Athens to be in line with other timelines of the project.

Below the updated and final pilot plan in Greece for UMC's by the Hellenic Red Cross is presented, as well as the plan for the piloting of real cases.

Pilot Plan

The pilot plan for unaccompanied migrant children in Greece by REDCROSS consists of two main parts: a tabletop exercise (first phase) and a field/simulation (second phase). In the tabletop exercise, a group of 20 people participated. The simulation exercise is scheduled to be held in April 2020, as said above, with a much broader participation and more functionalities that will be tested, including the version for Red Cross volunteers.

Timetable/plan and steps:

- [M18] - June 2019: Basic introduction and internal operation of the app
- [M19-21] - July – September 2019: Internal testing of the existing part of the mobile app. Comments sharing and modifications by technical partners
- [M22] – October 2019: Training and simulation/tabletop exercise (one day). Twenty participants attended training and tabletop exercise, that are key actors of the pilot organisation; Facility Managers, Case Managers, technical staff from the Social Welfare Division and Tracing department, Network Manager, etc. Technical partners also attended the exercise
- [M22-23] - October – November 2019: Modifications to the platform/app by the technical partners
- [M27] - March 2020: Final version of the platform/mobile app
- [M28] – April 2020: Training (one day) and field exercise (one day/same day) of the beta version of the ChildRescue platform/mobile app
- [M29] - May 2020: Public release of the ChildRescue platform/mobile app

2.3.2 Simulation/tabletop exercise

The tabletop exercise took place on the 11th of October 2019, at the training venue of the REDCROSS Social Welfare Dpt., at Voulis 38, Athens. The occasion of the tabletop exercise served also as an introduction to the ChildRescue platform and a training opportunity for the REDCROSS employees involved.

The actual exercise was organised in different parts according to the different actions foreseen for the REDCROSS with ChildRescue platform:

- Registration of UMC entering a REDCROSS facility (profiling) and monitoring of their presence
- Transfer of data between two facilities
- Integration of the ChildRescue platform to a tracing procedure

Pilot scenario

The procedure involved three main places of interest: The REDCROSS hosting facility in Athens, the hosting facility in Volos, the hosting facility in Kalavryta and the Tracing Service, under the Main Hypothesis that the ChildRescue platform is used in parallel to regular REDCROSS registration of UMC and that the ChildRescue platform contributes to the REDCROSS search and discovery of UMC mechanisms.

For the economy of the scenarios: the tabletop exercise has been planned to work as a preparatory phase for the field/real-time simulation scenario, while certain assumptions were made:

- When first entering the Shelter those UMC of age (above 15) consent to Search & Rescue (SAR) in case of emergency
- The UMC who consent are profiled by the shelter manager with ChildRescue
- When an UMC is placed in a REDCROSS hosting facility there are made efforts to restore contact with their family members
- All data registration and information sharing are done on the basis of the best interest of the child and in full respect to REDCROSS fundamental principles.

The first part of the pilot involved training on the ChildRescue platform and simulating integrating the ChildRescue platform in the profiling procedure once an UMC enters a REDCROSS hosting facility (placement by order of the Social Solidarity Center of the Ministry of Labor – in Greek E.K.K.A.).

Once a placement order is issued for an UMC, the receiving organisation - in that case the REDCROSS - receives together with the child all relative legal documentation. This information is on a later stage updated by the facility's social services to include further to the personal details and the legal background of the concerned UMC, his/her psychosocial background and best interest assessment details, as well as social media accounts and phone-numbers of both the UMC and his/her family members that can be in touch with. Gradual updating of the profiling information is required.

To simulate the procedure, 12 anonymised cases were chosen and 12 full casefiles were created with profiling information as described above. To preserve anonymisation, false names and personal details were used, while to better serve the hypothesis each case file came with a paper doll, some with distinctive physical features and clothing, representing the respective UMC involved.

All participants were split in pairs and each pair, representing a hosting facility, received two individual cases to simulate profiling through the ChildRescue platform. Data registration went well and some users uploaded also photos of the paper-dolls on the ChildRescue app.

The list created at each facility level could also be considered as a monitoring list enabling the caregivers to check the presence of the UMC on daily basis. The total of registrations, however, should be visible only on Organisation Coordinators level (two persons). By referring to the monitoring list, caregivers in the scenario could track the absence of an UMC during the first counting of the day and initiate procedures before the UMC was declared missing (second counting) – when an alert had been initiated and the UMC's place with the facility was considered vacant.

One problem of the profiling procedure is that it has to be repeated on different levels (authorities, NGOs, within an organisation etc.) Each hosting facility is keeping its own files and one of the scopes of profiling with ChildRescue is also to easily transfer data between facilities when needed. In the framework of the tabletop exercise, the REDCROSS received a note from EKKA, informing them that one of the UMC, reported missing from the hosting facility in Attica (during the aforementioned monitoring procedure), was found and has been relocated in Volos hosting facility. The Facility Manager in Attica was asked to transfer the profiling information of the UMC concerned to Volos facility. The coordinator of the organisation validated the request and green-lighted the transfer (orally as the respective part of the app was not ready) and the profiling data were successfully made available to the other facility environment.

The final part of the tabletop exercise was simulated on paper as the ChildRescue application encountered a technical difficulty.

According to the scenario the Tracing Service of the REDCROSS received a request about a missing child from the regional REDCROSS Department on Kos Island. While profiling the missing child using the ChildRescue platform, however, the case worker found out that there was a potential match with one of the UMC in the REDCROSS hosting facilities (one of the 12 UMC initially registered). This has not been tested between different organisations at this stage through the ChildRescue platform but this could be planned for the field exercise (2nd pilot phase).

The overall experience was positive with good potentials for future use under conditions. The main concerns had to do with the data protection issues and the legal implications, given that the REDCROSS pilot is dedicated to UMC and there are certain restrictions deriving from the relative Red Cross Movement and RFL network. The guardianship of the UMC in Greece remains a key issue and social workers working with the REDCROSS shelters underlined that the validation of data use should probably be on state level. It is also noted that ChildRescue could offer a great opportunity to unify data on different organisational levels, i.e. internally in the organisation. However, there is a concern on how sharing of information with other organisations would work. Social workers were also concerned about having to duplicate entries on different levels.

2.3.3 Field/simulation exercise

Sub-hypothesis: ChildRescue platform is used in parallel to regular REDCROSS procedures to locate UMC going missing from the REDCROSS hosting facility in Athens following an emergency incident (i.e. natural or manmade disaster)

Region of interest: Attica

Places involved: REDCROSS hosting facility for UMC at Alkiviadou str. - Athens, REDCROSS hosting facility in Volos, REDCROSS Multifunctional Center (MFC) in Athens, REDCROSS Tracing service, REDCROSS Branch on Kos island, REDCROSS Branch in Piraeus

Basic information about the facility in Athens

Full name: REDCROSS Accommodation Center for UMC (hosting facility)

Location: 4, Alkiviadou str. Athens

In house beneficiaries: 30

- sex: boys
- age group: 14-17

Key roles with the shelter: Hosting facility manager

Profiles of the missing children:

- Ahmad, 14 years old from Afghanistan. He has family in Germany, and they are in regular contact
- Mohamed, 16 years old also from Afghanistan. Has a big scar on his right arm. He has an uncle on Kos island. They have located each other through the REDCROSS RFL (see tabletop case).

Case scenario

At 9.20 a.m. an earthquake of 5.4 Richter scale degrees hits Attika. Following the relative protocol, the UMC and the personnel of the REDCROSS hosting facility evacuate the building. Everyone is ok, however damages of minor scale -a general water linkage and a collapsed pergola- result in traffic and confusion in the surrounding area. Telephone lines are overloaded and communication by phone is difficult. Some children are in distress.

Log-frame of the response/Steps

Step1: The manager of the hosting facility asks the social worker to check the UMC and confirm that there is no harm. The social worker counts the children with the ChildRescue to find out that 2 are missing.

Step 2: By consulting ChildRescue it is confirmed that the 2 children were present during the last count/taking presences at 7 o' clock.

Step 3: The manager informs the Organisation Coordinators via CR

In the meantime, a REDCROSS team of 4 persons (multidisciplinary) is developed using the collaboration space (standardised REDCROSS procedure – preparedness plan) to access the area.

Step 4: The head of the REDCROSS team and RFL receive via ChildRescue a notice about the missing UMC and send 2 volunteers to the area.

Step 5: The RFL releases the information in ChildRescue collaboration space that one of the missing UMC has a past tracing case – he has a relative on Kos island.

Step 6: Two REDCROSS volunteers and the social worker of the hosting facility scan the area on basis of the UMCs profiles in CR.

Potential points of interest:

Step 7: One UMC is located at the MFC. He went there to ask the interpreter to contact his family in Germany. ChildRescue case is updated and relative search is cancelled. The UMC receives Psychological First Aid (PFA).

Step 8: The MFC informs advanced users that they received a phone-call from the missing UMC uncle, and he was overwhelmed because he had heard about the earthquake.

Step 9: The second UMC with the relative on Kos island (Mohamed) is missing for almost 2 hours. The personnel and his peer group in the hosting facility are interviewed to gather additional information. A third UMC claims not to have seen the missing UMC since 8.30, right after breakfast.

Step 10: The REDCROSS takes necessary steps towards the responsible Greek authorities. The advanced user expands the research to the broader Attica region – selected volunteers and staff members (5) receive relative notices via CR.

Regular REDCROSS tracing procedure is ongoing in parallel - Trace the Face tool is also used.

Step 11: The uncle calls again and admits that he had asked the UMC to go and join him in order for them to return to try another way to the E.U.

In parallel, in Piraeus two old buildings have collapsed and the population there is in distress. Some people have minor injuries and the local branch has released teams in the area to assist the population.

Step 12: A foreign boy approaches one member of the team asking for assistance. Communication is difficult due to language problems.

Step 13: RED CROSS social worker in Piraeus Branch is informed and calls Hellenic Red Cross Headquarters (SWD). The UMC is encouraged to communicate with the hotlines' interpreter and admits that he was accommodated in Alkiviadou hosting facility.

Step 14: Child is escorted by the social worker to Piraeus Branch and is provided with PFA.

Step 15: The Branch social worker calls the hosting facility manager who in turn releases two team members (one social worker, one care giver) to escort the boy back to the shelter.

Step 16: Child is returned and ChildRescue platform is updated.

2.3.4 Real cases

Upon public release of the app, the ChildRescue app and platform will be in full use and piloted with 12 cases (UMs accommodated in a facility for minors run by the Hellenic Red Cross in Athens). It will be piloted there, before the launch of the public release, with the precondition of having granted first minors' consent for the use of their personal data. The aim is to proceed with proper registration of minors through the app.

The relevant procedures will run in parallel with the existing ones and will be in line with Red Cross Movement guidelines, ethics and principles on Protection.

Standard Operational Procedures will be drafted immediately after the pilot (simulation exercise), combining different Policies and Protocols within the Red Cross Movement, such as proper case management, use of personal data, search and rescue, Provision of Psychological First Aid, RFL and

RFL Code of Conduct, Protection, Community Engagement and Accountability, Dealing with Disasters etc.

Based on the above and focusing on a proper and efficient use of the app and platform, a series of trainings will be held, as follows:

- Training courses for simple users: 30-35 staff members (caregivers) from UM facilities run by the Hellenic Red Cross will attend concrete trainings on proper use
- Training courses for visitors: up to 20 volunteers with a background and expertise on psychosocial support provision, search & rescue and family links restoring will attend a series of trainings to get familiar with the app and the platform

During the process of real cases piloting, the validation framework will be followed, and monitoring will be made by Organisation Coordinators regularly, aiming to proceed -when necessary- with adjustments, amendments, new actions taking, etc.

This phase will include the following actors:

- Visitors (Trained Volunteers)
- Simple Users (Caregivers)
- Organisation coordinators
- Hosting facility managers
- Organisation Owner

During this phase the following infrastructure of the Hellenic Red Cross will be used:

- UM facilities/shelters
- Volunteer teams
- Hellenic Red Cross fleet, especially search and rescue vehicles and radio networks

3 Evaluation / validation of pilots and real implementation

3.1 Updated performance/validation indicators

3.1.1 Changes from 1st iteration (if any)

The KPIs included in the 1st iteration had already been updated from those initially proposed in the D4.1 - Validation Framework, after bilateral meetings with the pilot organisations. Therefore, KPIs that were marked in D4.2 as “non-applicable” for a certain pilot organisation or even all of them, have been totally removed in this deliverable, for clarity purposes. Additionally, minor updates in the phrasing have been made, to make KPIs more tangible, while some KPIs assessed as not adding important value to the validation of the platform have been removed. The numbering has been preserved for consistency and easier comparison at the final validation stage.

3.1.2 Missing children – Greece (SoC)

The KPIs for SoC and their values are enlisted in the following table.

Table 3-1 KPIs for SoC

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value
PI.01	number of ChildRescue mobile application downloads monthly	N/A	0
PI.02	number of aggregated ChildRescue mobile application downloads	N/A	0
PI.03	average number of notified citizens through SMS, social media (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter) and ChildRescue mobile users per case	average number of citizens notified per case through SMS and social media (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter) before ChildRescue - #SMS sent and #views per social media post	200.000
PI.05	average number of notifications sent through ChildRescue per case	N/A	0
PI.06	average number of citizens providing feedback per case before mobile application launch	average number of citizens providing feedback per case before mobile application launch (excluding family members)	4

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value
PI.07	average number of citizens providing feedback through the ChildRescue app per case	N/A	0
PI.08	ratio: number of citizens who provide feedback through any channel to number of sent SMS notifications, social media views and ChildRescue mobile users per case	number of citizens who provide feedback to number of sent SMS notifications and social media views (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter) per case	4/200.000
PI.09	ratio: average number of citizens receiving notification through ChildRescue to total number of mobile application downloads per case	N/A	0
PI.10	ratio: number of personal notifications sent vs the total area covered (per case)	#SMS subscribers (per DoA) vs Greece area	13.700/ 132.049km ²
PI.11	ratio: number of valid (in the context of ChildRescue terminology) feedback to total number of submitted feedback	N/A	0
PI.13	number of new volunteers who applied encouraged by ChildRescue	N/A	0
PI.15	number of organisations using or interacting with ChildRescue	number of pilots	3
PI.16	number of EU organisations, in countries except Greece and Belgium, using or	N/A	0

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value
	interacting with ChildRescue		
PI.17	number of organisations using or interacting with ChildRescue during missing children investigations	number of pilots involved in missing children use case	2
PI.20	average number of posts and announcements made in the ChildRescue collaboration space per case	N/A	0
PI.26	average time between reporting of disappearance and locating the missing child	average time currently needed between the day of disappearance and locating the missing child	6 days
PI.27	average time needed for volunteer/search and rescue team formation per case	average time currently needed for volunteer/search and rescue team formation per case	1 hour
PI.28	average time needed for citizens to get informed for a case for the first time, after the decision for dissemination	average time currently needed for citizens to get informed for a case for the first time, after the decision for dissemination (from dissemination approval from police to amber alert)	15 minutes
PI.30	average time needed for examining and retrieving information from old cases of the same child	N/A	0
PI.34	number of missing children real-life cases piloting	N/A	0
PI.36	average time needed for retrieving information of repeated disappearance cases	average time currently needed for retrieving information of repeated	5 minutes

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value
		disappearance cases (old cases of same child)	
PI.38	response organisation human effort and direct costs per case	current human effort and direct costs per case	6 man-days
PI.40	qualitative: estimating how much ChildRescue assists the organisations and operators on understanding better the behavioural and navigational patterns behind disappearances	(no baseline to be defined – the indicator is expressed by a percentage of improvement in comparison to the initial/current status)	N/A – progress will be defined with self-evaluation
PI.41	qualitative: estimating if ChildRescue contributed significantly to cases' resolution	N/A	N/A – progress will be defined with self-evaluation

3.1.3 Missing children – Belgium (CF)

The KPIs for CF are enlisted in the following table.

Table 3-2 KPIs for Child Focus

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value
PI.01	number of ChildRescue mobile application downloads monthly	N/A	0
PI.02	number of aggregated ChildRescue mobile application downloads	N/A	0
PI.03	average number of notified mobile users per case through social media (Facebook and Twitter) and ChildRescue notifications	average number of citizens notified per case through social media (Facebook and Twitter) before ChildRescue – only #views per social media post applies to CF	198.154

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value
PI.05	number of notifications sent through ChildRescue per case	N/A	0
PI.06	average number of citizens providing feedback per case	average number of citizens providing feedback per case before mobile application launch	3 testimonies
PI.07	average number of citizens providing feedback through the ChildRescue app per case	N/A	0
PI.08	ratio: number of citizens who provide feedback through any channel to number of sent SMS notifications, social media views and ChildRescue mobile users per case	number of citizens who provide feedback to number of sent SMS notifications and social media views (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter) per case	3/198.154
PI.09	ratio: average number of citizens receiving notification through ChildRescue to total number of mobile application downloads per case	N/A	0
PI.10	ratio: number of personal notifications sent to specific locations vs the total area covered per case	N/A	0
PI.11	ratio: number of valid (in the context of ChildRescue terminology) feedback to total number of submitted feedback	N/A	0
PI.13	number of new volunteers who applied encouraged by ChildRescue	N/A	0
PI.14	qualitative: estimate progress in public perception of the organisation's activities	existing surveys on public perception of CF, if it is innovative etc	90% of the Belgian population (+18) sees Child Focus as 'forward thinking', 60% as

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value
			innovative (Brand Asset Evaluator)
PI.15	number of organisations using or interacting with ChildRescue	number of pilots	3
PI.16	number of EU organisations, in countries except Greece and Belgium, using or interacting with ChildRescue	N/A	0
PI.17	number of organisations using or interacting with ChildRescue during missing children investigations	number of pilots involved in missing children use case	2
PI.19	number of organisations and internal departments using or interacting with ChildRescue during activities pertaining unaccompanied migrant minors	N/A	0
PI.20	average number of posts and announcements made in the ChildRescue collaboration space per case	N/A	0
PI.21	qualitative: improvement in information integrity and data consistency	(no baseline to be defined – the indicator is expressed by a percentage of improvement in comparison to the initial/current status)	N/A – progress will be defined with self-evaluation
PI.26	average time between reporting of disappearance and locating the missing child	average time currently needed between reporting of disappearance and locating the missing child	1 - 2 days 37,54% 2 - 7 days 35,89% 7 – 30 days 17,24% 1 - 6 months 7,44% + 6 months 1,30%
PI.27	average time needed for volunteer team formation per case	average time currently needed for volunteer team formation per case – current	60 minutes

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value
		process includes phone calls and SMS	
PI.28	average time needed for citizens to get informed for a case for the first time, after the decision for dissemination	average time currently needed for citizens to get informed for a case for the first time, after the decision/approval for dissemination	Locally disseminated paper posters: 210 minutes Social media: 40 minutes
PI.30	average time needed for examining and retrieving information from old cases of the same child	N/A	0
PI.34	number of missing children real-life cases piloting	N/A	0
PI.36	average time needed for retrieving information of repeated disappearance cases	average time currently needed for retrieving information of repeated disappearance cases – electronic system supports exact name search	1-2 minutes
PI.38	response organisation human effort and direct costs per case	current human effort and direct costs per case	1000 euro
PI.40	qualitative: estimating how much ChildRescue assists in the organisations' and operators' knowledge and understanding about disappearances as a phenomenon	(no baseline to be defined – the indicator is expressed by a percentage of improvement in comparison to the initial/current status)	N/A – progress will be defined with self-evaluation
PI.41	qualitative: estimating if ChildRescue contributed significantly to cases' resolution	N/A	N/A – progress will be defined with self-evaluation

3.1.4 Unaccompanied migrant children (RED CROSS)

The KPIs for REDCROSS, are enlisted in the following table. The operations of REDCROSS are not always open to the general public and discreet investigations are conducted by volunteers of the REDCROSS. For consistency reasons, the wording 'citizens*' in the following KPIs has not been changed, however wherever an asterisk is appended, it indicates 'volunteers'.

Table 3-3 KPIs for REDCROSS

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Values
PI.01	number of ChildRescue mobile application downloads monthly	N/A	0
PI.02	number of aggregated ChildRescue mobile application downloads	N/A	0
PI.03	average number of notified mobile users through mail, phone call and ChildRescue notifications per case	average number of mobile users notified per case through mail and phone call before ChildRescue	2-10 volunteers depending on capacity and location of Branch Office <u>for case of missing child</u> <u>10-20 for emergency case (depending on location etc)</u>
PI.05	number of notifications sent through ChildRescue per case	N/A	0
PI.06	average number of citizens* providing feedback per case	average number of citizens* providing feedback per case before mobile application launch	0 – citizens actively don't provide information to RC
PI.07	average number of citizens* providing feedback through the ChildRescue app per case	N/A	0
PI.08	ratio: number of citizens* who provide feedback through any channel to number of sent SMS notifications, social media views and	number of citizens* who provide feedback to number of sent SMS notifications and social media views (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter) per case	0

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Values
	ChildRescue mobile users per case		
PI.09	ratio: average number of citizens* receiving notification through ChildRescue to total number of mobile application downloads per case	N/A	0
PI.10	ratio: number of personal notifications sent to specific locations vs the total area covered per case	#citizens notified personally vs Greece area	20/132.049 km ²
PI.11	ratio: number of valid feedback to total number of submitted feedback	N/A	0
PI.13	number of new volunteers who applied encouraged by ChildRescue	N/A	0
PI.15	number of organisations using or interacting with ChildRescue	number of pilots	3
PI.16	number of EU organisations, in countries except Greece and Belgium, using or interacting with ChildRescue	N/A	0
PI.17	number of organisations using or interacting with ChildRescue during missing children investigations	number of pilots involved in missing children use case	2
PI.18	number of unaccompanied migrant	N/A	0

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Values
	minors matched to existing profiles		
PI.19	number of organisations and internal departments using or interacting with ChildRescue during activities pertaining unaccompanied migrant minors	N/A	0
PI.20	average number of posts and announcements made in the ChildRescue collaboration space per case	N/A	0
PI.21	qualitative: improvement in information integrity and data consistency	(no baseline to be defined – the indicator is expressed by a percentage of improvement in comparison to the initial/current status)	N/A
PI.22	total number of unaccompanied migrant minor profiles registered in ChildRescue	N/A	0
PI.23	average time needed to inform the relevant stakeholder about a vacancy in a hosting facility	average time currently needed to inform the relevant stakeholder about a vacancy in a hosting facility – written formal briefing to EKKA and prosecutor	1 day
PI.24	average time needed to detect the absence of an unaccompanied migrant minor from the hosting facility	average time currently needed to detect the absence of an unaccompanied migrant minor from the hosting facility	8 or 16 hours for first notice of absence // 24 hours for confirmation of absence

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Values
PI.25	average time between issuing a Tracing request and finding information the missing child	average time currently needed between issuing a Tracing request and finding information about the missing child	immediately to max 6 months - (afterwards it is very unlikely that any information will be found)
PI.26	average time between reporting of disappearance and locating the missing child	average time currently needed between reporting of disappearance and locating the missing child	3 - 10 days in case of emergency
PI.27	average time needed for volunteer/search and rescue team formation per case	average time currently needed for volunteer/search and rescue team formation per case	1-2 hours –through messenger and what’s up applications
PI.28	average time needed for citizens* to get informed for a case for the first time, after the decision for dissemination	average time currently needed for citizens* to get informed for a case for the first time, after the decision for dissemination	currently N/A
PI.30	average time needed for examining and retrieving information from old cases of the same child	average time currently needed for examining and retrieving information from old cases similar to current	15 minutes - all search done by EKKA
PI.34	number of missing children real-life cases piloting	N/A	0
PI.36	average time needed for retrieving information of repeated disappearance cases ¹	average time currently needed for retrieving information of repeated disappearance cases	40 minutes

¹In the case of REDCROSS and a hosted unaccompanied minor case, this PI refers to a minor who returns to a shelter she/he has been hosted before

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Values
PI.38	response organisation human effort and direct costs per case	current human effort and direct costs per case	N/A
PI.39	qualitative: estimated improvement in statistics regarding unaccompanied migrant minors	(no baseline to be defined – the indicator is expressed by a percentage of improvement in comparison to the initial/current status)	N/A
PI.40	qualitative: estimating how much ChildRescue assists in the organisations' and operators' knowledge and understanding about disappearances as a phenomenon	(no baseline to be defined – the indicator is expressed by a percentage of improvement in comparison to the initial/current status)	N/A – progress will be defined with self-evaluation
PI.41	qualitative: estimating if ChildRescue contributed significantly to cases resolution	N/A	N/A – progress will be defined with self-evaluation

3.2 Evaluation of the piloting phase

3.2.1 Changes from 1st iteration

During the first tabletop exercise, both quantitative and qualitative methods were used to evaluate the usability and functionality of the ChildRescue app and platform. Participating staff members were given the opportunity to give in-depth feedback by holding focus groups, utilising an open-ended question guideline to ensure comparability in all three organisations. Additionally, surveys were conducted to gain insight into specific aspects, such as the accessibility of the app and platform to all people and to ensure the intuitive use of the ChildRescue solution. After the analysis of the data from the first piloting phase, some changes have been made. Despite the overall high scores of the app and platform in the surveys and the expressed positive attitude towards ChildRescue in the focus group (cf. D4.3), some small changes were necessary to adapt the existing app and platform. Additionally, the evaluation tool, namely the survey itself, had to be adapted to be more suitable for all participating organisations. It has become apparent that the different workflows in Child Focus, which is partly due to the legal framework in Belgium, led to the relatively high amount of 'I don't know' answers on specific items (n=17) in comparison to the 'I don't know' answers from the Greek organisations (HRC n=1, SoC n=5).

Consequently, a call with Child Focus partners was held to ensure that the survey would be phrased in a manner that allows the surveyed to answer most questions. Furthermore, 'not applicable' was added

as an option in addition to 'I don't know' to correctly reflect differing workflows. Through this addition, it is assumed that the second set of surveys will be able to show if the respondent actually does not know the answer to an item or cannot answer because the feature is not available in the workflow of their organisation. In order to eliminate any insecurities about the answers on the time needed for specific workflows (e.g. creating a case file or informing the public) without the use of ChildRescue, Child Focus suggested to stress that the items relate to personal estimations and not hard facts. This has been implemented by replacing the verb 'answer' with 'estimate' for all items relating to time periods. The item 'number of investigation activities in irrelevant locations' was further deleted altogether, since the majority of survey takers from all organisations have indicated 'I don't know' in response to that specific item.

Other issues that have come to light during the analysis of the first evaluation phase are the lack of understanding of the data protection protocol, as well as issues with the alarm signals in the first tabletop exercise. Consequently, the existing data protection protocol should be explained in more detail during the second phase of exercises. In order to enable an evaluation of the volume and sound of the alarm signals the participants of the second piloting exercises should also be reminded to put their phones on 'loud'.

The desired changes to the design and functions of the app and platform that were highlighted by the participants from the first evaluation phase were communicated to the partners during the technical meeting in Athens in January 2020 (cf. table 4). Changes that were alluded to in multiple organisations were printed in bold. Additionally, the size of the text as well as the contrast between the background colouring and the text should be reconsidered and the size of the photo was considered to be too small. The colouring scheme has consequently been changed to include black writing on a white background, which makes it easier to read.

Table 3-4 Necessary changes highlighted in the first piloting phase

Piloting organisation	Alterations to the design of the app	Alterations to the usability of the app	Alterations to the design of the platform	Alterations to the usability of the platform
Smile of the Child	'no need to register' and GDPR before registration, inform user that GPS needs to be switched on at all times, larger photo of missing child, text on SoC needs revision	Clear definition of 'location' when providing information and appreciative message after providing information, menu not always available	add 'age' as input that can be shown in app, desktop notifications for case managers,	additional information on input, option to edit alert , option for case manager to view how many users received notifications/ are active

<p>Child Focus</p>	<p>Inform users that GPS needs to be switched on at all times, only first name of child displayed, add information on why and when alert was deactivated, multilingual alerts, active alerts displayed first</p>	<p>Lift completely anonymous status of people providing information to prevent abuse, exclude children from using app by introducing minimum age</p>	<p>Some lines for input only partially visible, rephrase 'psychological issues', add other categories, add previous alert for same child (only visible for case manager)</p>	<p>allow multiple indications, save new case without publishing in process of case creation, multilingual alerts, download preview of alerts to send to colleagues</p>
<p>Hellenic Red Cross</p>	<p>Information pop-up 'no need to register' and GDPR before registration, create pop-up window to inform users if the information provided is incorrect or insufficient</p>	<p>Menu not always available</p>	<p>Add 'unknown' and 'other' to categories, rephrase sensitive sections, add other categories, date of birth not always available (add estimated age)</p>	<p>Location last seen needs to be given by caregiver, possibility to add also phone numbers of family members (not just child's number) for direct contact, option to edit alert</p>

3.2.2 Evaluation of the real cases pilot phase

For the second phase of the piloting evaluation, an additional online survey for the volunteers as well as an open-ended interview guideline for the participating staff members has been developed. Additionally, the survey for the staff members from the first phase will be included in the second phase with the implemented changes as described in 3.2.1.

In addition to the first tabletop exercises, the second piloting phase will also include volunteers from the organisations, who will be surveyed online in order to get feedback on the functions of the app pertaining to their role. Additionally, staff members will receive the part of the altered survey from the first tabletop exercise relating to their workflow **without** ChildRescue. This will happen before the real case pilot exercise in order to estimate the time needed for workflows with the current process, which was question block 5 of the whole survey, used during the first tabletop exercise (cf. Table 3-5). After the real case pilot exercise, the long version of the altered survey for the staff members (including all 5 question blocks of the questionnaire) with questions on their workflow **with** the use of ChildRescue will be handed out in order to gain insight on the perception of the innovation potential of the ChildRescue solution (cf. Table 3-6). In conclusion, question block 5 will be handed out twice during the process of the second piloting phase: once asking about the workflow **without** ChildRescue before the real case exercise, once asking about the workflow **with** ChildRescue after the real case exercise.

The second survey, which will ask about the workflow **with** ChildRescue will also include the other four question blocks of the survey, whereas the first version (which asks about the workflow **without** ChildRescue) will only contain the question block 5, depicted in Table 3-5. Consequently, the first survey will be a lot shorter. The evaluation will take place during the second exercises in all three organisations and any potential changes will be communicated with the partners to ensure they can be taken into account before releasing the final version of the ChildRescue app and platform to the public.

Table 3-5 Questions part 5 pertaining to the workflows without ChildRescue before the real case exercise

5. How would you rate the following **without** the use of the ChildRescue App/Platform (if your organisation does not work in the way described, please answer 'not applicable')

	0-1	2-5	6-10	11-15	16 or more	Don't know	Not applicable
average time between reporting of disappearance and locating the missing child (please estimate in hrs)							
average time needed for volunteer/search and rescue team formation per case (please estimate in hrs)							
average time needed for citizens to get informed for a case for the first time, after the decision for dissemination (please estimate in hrs)							
average number of old cases matched to current case							
average time needed for examining and retrieving information from old cases similar to current (please estimate in hrs)							
average time needed for creating complete case reports (please estimate in hrs)							

Table 3-6 Questions part 5 pertaining to the workflows with ChildRescue after the real case exercise

5. How would you rate the following **with** the use of the ChildRescue App/Platform (if your organisation does not work in the way described, please answer 'not applicable')

	0-1	2-5	6-10	11-15	16 or more	Don't know	Not applicable
average time between reporting of disappearance and locating the missing child (please estimate in hrs)							
average time needed for volunteer/search and rescue team formation per case (please estimate in hrs)							
average time needed for citizens to get informed for a case for the first time, after the decision for dissemination (please estimate in hrs)							
average number of old cases matched to current case							
average time needed for examining and retrieving information from old cases similar to current (please estimate in hrs)							
average time needed for creating complete case reports (please estimate in hrs)							

4 Conclusion

The main focus of this deliverable was the compilation of the ChildRescue trial scenarios in the context of Tasks 4.2-4.4, which will serve as a guideline for the next steps of WP4 –“Missing Persons Cases Piloting and Evaluation”, leading to the final release and evaluation of the platform in terms of added value for the organisations. Specifically, each pilot developed trial scenarios to be used for a series of simulation and field exercises in order to test the ChildRescue Platform. In addition, the performance indicators were further specified, which will be put to test when the platform is operational, while the evaluation plan for the pilots was defined. Finally, the End Users’ Handbook has been elaborated, that describes the role of each user and the way to use the platform. The precise results from the simulation and field exercises will be updated through deliverable D4.5.

Annex I: End Users' Handbook

I.1 Introduction

The End User's Handbook is a simple and user-friendly guide containing all information required by a user so that he or she can operate successfully the current version of the mobile application and the platform. In other words, the presented Handbook describes the complete set of functionalities and supported roles in the 2nd release of the ChildRescue software package.

Several changes have emerged from the 1st release of the Handbook, namely: As expected, a number of functionalities have been added with the completion of the software development activities and the implementation of all foreseen components and user roles. Screenshots from components that were available at the 1st release, have been replaced with updated ones, as minor changes in the user interface and wording have been applied.

Regarding the structure of the guide, the Mobile App Users' Handbook follows the same structure as in the 1st iteration, with the addition of a section for the Volunteers' application. However, the web application Handbook has been restructured for usability purposes and to avoid repetitions.

Thus, the 2nd iteration of the Handbook is structured as follows:

Mobile Application Users: The instructions are categorised by role. For each user role the available functionalities are presented per screen. More specifically, the supported mobile app end users' roles are:

- Visitor (mobile app)
- Simple User (mobile app)
- Volunteer (mobile app)

Web Application Users: The instructions are categorised by functionality/screen. The web user roles each functionality is available for, are appropriately indicated. A table with available actions in each page is also included inside each section. The supported roles are:

- Organisation Owner (web app)
- Organisation Coordinator (web app)
- Case Manager (web app)
- Hosting Facility Manager (web app)
- Network Manager (web app)

The ChildRescue administrator operations are fully supported as well, but this role is not considered to be in the end users' user-group and thus, it is not included in this document.

I.2 Description of how to use the ChildRescue mobile app as "Visitor"

The visitor is an unregistered user who installs the app and can use a limited set of functionalities, without registration.

I.2.1 Welcome

Once the user installs the app, s/he is presented with two welcome screens: the first one (Figure I-1) provides the title of the ChildRescue project and the second one (Figure I-2) a brief description on how the user could get involved with ChildRescue. The user can proceed with the app either by pressing the "SKIP" button in the first case, or by pressing "GOT IT" in the second case.

Figure I-1 Welcome Title

Figure I-2 Welcome Description

I.2.2 Login-Register

As soon as the user visits the welcome page, she/he is redirected to the login screen (Figure I-3), where she can choose whether she will register into the app or not. In case she wants to register, she clicks on the link "New user? Sign up" and she is transferred to the registration form (Figure I-4). In case she doesn't want to register, she can continue navigating anonymously by pressing the "SKIP" button.

Figure I-3 Login

Figure I-4 Register

I.2.3 Dashboard

The scope of the dashboard (Figure I-5) is to provide a general overview of the main parts of the mobile app, so that the user will be able to access them. The dashboard includes a) alerts about cases of missing children close to the location of the user, b) information about the organisations involved into the project, and c) instructions on how a user can become a volunteer. In addition to the main view of the dashboard, the users can use the navigation area at the bottom (the black area covering the bottom of the screen) in order to access the aforementioned information and the navigation area at the top (the black area covering the top of the screen) either for providing information for a specific case or going back to login screen. Figure I-7 displays a list view of the available organisations, which is displayed by pressing the “Organisations” card item, while Figure I-9 depicts the view that provides guidelines regarding the process of how the simple users can become volunteers by choosing the “BECOME A VOLUNTEER” card item. Both card items are available from the dashboard view, as shown in Figure I-5. Furthermore, some general information of the app is available via the overflow menu, which is placed at the top right corner of the screen, where two new sections have been incorporated in order for the users to be able to navigate through the app in a more flexible way. More specifically,

not only the language selection has been provided as shown in Figure I-6, but also an instruction guide has also been included as depicted in Figure I-8.

Figure I-5 Dashboard

Figure I-7 Organisation List View

Figure I-6 Language Selection

Figure I-8 User Manual

Figure I-9 Become a Volunteer

I.2.4 Provide Information for specific alert

The user can provide feedback about a specific case by clicking on the alert card of the specific case on her dashboard. As soon as the user clicks on the alert card, she is provided with the feedback form (Figure I-10, Figure I-11). The user fills out the form with the relevant information and presses the "SUBMIT INFORMATION" button in order to submit her feedback. In addition to the previous version the user can also send a picture, which might be useful for a specific case. For this purpose, two options are available, so that the user can either pick an image from the local gallery or capture a photo and subsequently send it to the case manager. The aforementioned new functionality is depicted in Figure I-11.

Figure I-10 Provide Information Complete Form (1/2)

Figure I-11 Provide Information Complete Form (2/2)

I.2.5 Provide Information

Besides the general information that is available through the dashboard view, the user can provide information on her own, in case she wants to provide feedback related to a missing child case. To do so, they are redirected to the respective view (Figure I-12) by pressing the “info” icon from the top bar as shown up in Figure I-5. The user selects “YES, I HAVE SOME INFORMATION” in order to access all open and active cases (Figure I-12) and she is provided with the relevant cases (Figure I-13). By clicking on the relevant case button, the user is provided with the relevant information of the case (Figure I-14). This view includes information related to the missing child, which will be helpful for the public. Such information is physical attributes of the child like height and weight, a summarized description of the case and important dates like the child’s date of birth and the date in which the child was disappeared.

Figure I-12 Provide Information Step 1

Figure I-13 Provide Information Step 2

Figure I-14 Provide Information

I.3 Description of how to use the ChildRescue mobile app as “Simple User”

In the current section, the functionalities of the simple user (or registered user) will be presented. Most of the features are common with the unregistered users. Additionally, the simple user is provided with personalised navigation and other functionalities.

I.3.1 Login-Register

The welcome view (Figure I-2) as well as the login and register forms (Figure I-3, Figure I-4) remain the same as they are presented in the previous section. The user fills out her credentials in order to register into the mobile app and become a simple user (Figure I-15). Right after the successful registration, users will be led automatically to the login screen in order to start their navigation as registered users by providing their credentials.

Figure I-15 Register Example

I.3.2 Dashboard

Once the user logs into the mobile app, she is provided with the main dashboard (Figure I-16). At the top area, the login icon has been replaced with the logout one, while the full name of the registered user is displayed right below the title of the app at the top left of the screen. Moreover, in the alert cards, by tapping on three dots icon, the user is provided with additional functionalities related to the case alerts. These include the "Provide Info" which allows users to send feedback for a specific case directly from the main dashboard, and the "Follow" functionality (Figure I-17, Figure I-18) which enables the user to follow that specific case. By clicking the "Follow" label, any further notification in the future, which is related to this case, will be delivered to the user no matter what their location will be, and the relevant alert card will be pinned on her dashboard. Furthermore, at the bottom area, an item called "profile" has been added and once the users press it, her profile is displayed (Figure I-19). It should be highlighted that in the second release, the registered user can edit or delete her profile at any time by using the respective buttons.

Figure I-16 Dashboard Registered User

Figure I-17 Follow Case

Figure I-18 List of Followed Cases

I.3.3 User account

The user account contains the personal info of the registered user and a list view of the feedback that the user has provided in the past.

Figure I-19 Profile Registered User

I.3.4 Provide Information for specific alert

The user is able to provide feedback about a specific case by clicking on the alert card of the specific case on her dashboard, the same way as the unregistered users. As soon as the user clicks on the alert card, she is provided with the feedback form. The user fills out the form with the relevant information and presses the "SUBMIT INFORMATION" button in order to submit her feedback.

I.3.5 Provide Information

Besides the general information that is available through the dashboard view, the user can provide information on her own, in case she wants to provide feedback related to a missing child case. To do so, they are redirected to the respective view (Figure I-12) by pressing the "info" icon from the top bar as shown up in Figure I-16, the same way as the unregistered users.

I.4 Description of how to use the ChildRescue mobile app as “Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Member (Leader)”

In the current section, the functionalities of the volunteer users will be presented. Most of the features are common with the registered users, however, there is one differentiation with respect to the role of the user, since the volunteers cannot navigate through the app anonymously. Therefore, all these members will have to use their credentials, so that they can have access to the entire app. Moreover, due to the fact that the majority of the functionalities are the same with those that are available for the registered users, only the new parts of the app that are intended for the volunteers will be presented in the following sections.

I.4.1 Dashboard and case management

Once the user logs into the mobile app, the main dashboard (Figure I-20) is displayed. It can be observed that the navigation menus along with the content of the view is almost the same as it is in the previous roles. The only differentiation is the existence of two additional card items in the “CHILDRESCUE INFO” section. To begin with, the “Cases” card item represents the open cases for which a volunteer has received an invitation to actively participate in. In other words, and as depicted in Figure I-21, in the tab “JOIN REQUEST” the list of cases for which an invitation has been sent to the volunteer is displayed. Apart from that, another list (“JOINED CASES”) with the accepted requests is also provided, and it represents all these cases for which the volunteer is an active member and contributes to. Finally, for the “JOINED Cases” the user’s location can be sent to the Network Manager at any time.

Figure I-20 Volunteers Main Dashboard

Figure I-21 Case Management

I.4.2 Collaboration Space

While in the previous section (I.4.1) the whole case management functionality was demonstrated, in the current section the collaboration space part will be presented. More specifically, the cases that constitute the collaboration space are those that have already been joined from the volunteers (Figure I-22). Consequently, the user has two options in terms of navigation.

The first option would be to send information with respect to a specific case to the Network Manager directly, by clicking the info icon at the top left corner of the card. This action will redirect the user to the respective form (Figure I-23), which is partially differentiated from the one presented in registered user's section (Figure I-10, Figure I-11). Finally, the user fills out the form with the relevant information and presses the "SUBMIT INFORMATION" button in order to submit her feedback.

The second option is to check the overall feedback that has been sent by the Network Manager in respect of specific case. For this purpose, a view that includes both a map and a timeline with specific case information is provided (Figure I-24). From the same view, the user can also receive information

related to the active members of a case and the feedback that has sent to the Network Manager by “MEMBERS” and “FEED” tab accordingly.

Figure I-22 Collaboration Space

Figure I-23 Feed to Network Manager

Figure I-24 Space Info

I.5 Description of how to use the platform as Web User

I.5.1 Login and general actions available in all pages

When the user types the URL address of the ChildRescue web application, she is directed to the login page (Figure I-25), where she is asked for her registered email address and password to access her account.

Figure I-25 ChildRescue Web Login

Once logged in, the user can perform some general actions available in all pages, including logout and profile management (Figure I-26).

Table I-1 General Actions

What to do	How
Hide/Show Side-menu	Use the floating menu icon in the upper left area to show/hide the side-menu.
Logout from platform	Click on the user profile area in the upper right corner, which is available in all pages. Select 'Logout' from the drop-down menu.
View my profile	Click on the user profile area in the upper right corner, which is available in all pages. Select 'Profile' from the drop-down menu. You are directed to your profile page where you can find all the profile information.
Edit my profile	From the 'Profile' page, use the pencil icon to edit all fields. Use the tick icon to save changes or the 'x' icon to discard changes and return.

Figure I-26 User Profile View and Edit page

I.5.2 Platform Browsing

I.5.2.1 "Dashboard" page

Available for: Case Manager, Organisation Coordinator, Facility Manager

Once the user logs in successfully, she is directed to the main Dashboard. The Dashboard provides a general overview of the ChildRescue Platform. It presents important information in numbers regarding the facility (for HFMs) or the investigation (for CMs, CCs). It contains a grid with the active missing children cases, a list with recent alerts and recent facts. A flexible menu on the left side helps the user to navigate in the various screens of the application (Figure I-27).

Table I-2 "Dashboard" Page Actions

What to do	How
View key information for the organisation’s cases	The numbers of active cases, active alerts and total facts are available on the upper area of the Default view.
View grid of the organisation’s active cases	It is in the left area of the Default view. You can click on the case thumbnail to be directed to the "Child Record" page.
View list with recent alerts	A list with the 5 latest alerts for the organisation’s cases is available in the up-right column of the Default view. It includes the case ID, alert Date and alert Time. You can click on the alert to open a popup window with more details.
View list with recent facts	A list with the 5 latest facts for the organisation’s cases is available in the bottom-right column of the Default

view. It includes the case ID, fact creation Date and Time, and the fact Source. You can click on the fact to open a popup window with more details.

Figure I-27 Case Manager Dashboard Page

1.5.2.2 Organisation Management

Available for: Organisation Owner

The Organisation Owner can view and edit the organisation’s information, which are available to all ChildRescue users. This information includes: Contact Details (Phone Number, Email, Address), Social Media Profiles (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter), instructions on the process to become a volunteer, the organisation’s description, and instructions for citizens on the actions they should take when they spot a possibly missing child (Figure I-28).

Table I-3 "Organisation Management" Page Actions

What to do	How
View the organisation details	It is the Default view. You can view all the fields of the organisation’s profile
Edit organisation details	Use the pencil icon to edit all fields of the organisation’s profile. Use the tick icon to save changes or the ‘x’ icon to discard changes and return.

Figure I-28 Organisation Management Page

1.5.2.3 Facility Management

Available for: Organisation Owner

The Organisation Owner has an overview of the facilities registered under the organisation, either if they host children or not. From this page, the Owner can edit the registered facilities or add new ones. The facility information includes: Name, Email, Address, whether it is a hosting facility or not (e.g. call centre), the hosting capacity (option available only for hosting facilities) (Figure I-29).

Since every member of the organisation needs to be assigned to a facility, the facility creation is a necessary first step for each organisation.

Table I-4 "Facility Management" Page Actions

What to do	How
View list of the organisation’s facilities	It is the Default view. You can sort the values by clicking each header. You can choose the number of facilities displayed per page.
View facility details	By clicking anywhere on the row of a facility you are directed to the Facility Details page, where you can find all the information and a map with the location of the facility.
Edit facility	<u>Two ways to edit a registered facility</u> 1. From the “Facility Management” page: Use the pencil icon to edit all fields of a facility. Click ‘UPDATE’ save changes or ‘CANCEL’ to discard changes and return to the Facility Details page.

	2. From the Facility Details page: By clicking on the 'EDIT' button to edit all fields of a user's profile. Click 'UPDATE' save changes or 'CANCEL' to discard changes and return to the Facility Details page.
Enable/Disable a user	Use the green/red slider icon to set the status of the user. By disabling, the user is prevented from logging in until he or she is enabled.
Add new user to the organisation	By clicking the button 'ADD USER', you are prompted to fill in information about the user and assign him or her to a facility. Volunteers are excluded from the facility assignment. directed to the add user page. Fill in the field. Click 'SAVE' to create the new user or click 'CANCEL' to discard changes and return.

ID	Name	Email	Phone	Address	Is hosting	Capacity	Actions
7	SoutheasternCenter	-	-	1 Spyrou Loui Str, Marousi, 15124	🏠	-	✎
1	Επιστροφής Αοιός	-	-	Επιστροφής Αοιός 18	🏠	-	✎

Figure I-29 Facility Management Page

1.5.2.4 User Management

Available for: Organisation Owner

The Organisation Owner has an overview of the users registered to the organisation. These are users officially related to the organisation, as employees or official volunteers. Only after their registration by the Organisation Owner, will they be able to use the web platform or the volunteer application (according to their assigned user role). The user information includes: Role (Coordinator, Case Manager, Facility Manager, Network manager, Volunteer), Facility (selection from the list of facilities registered to the organisation), Email, Address, Password, First Name, Last Name, City, Address, Description (free text) (Figure I-30).

Table I-5 "User Management" Page Actions

What to do	How
View list of the organisation's users	It is the Default view. You can sort the values by clicking each header. You can choose the number of users displayed per page.
View user details	By clicking anywhere on the row of a user you are directed to the User Details page, where you can find all the profile fields and a map with the location of the user.
Edit user	<p><u>Two ways to edit a user's profile</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. From the "User Management" page: Use the pencil icon to edit all fields of a user's profile. Click 'UPDATE' save changes or 'CANCEL' to discard changes and return to the User Details page. 2. From the User Details page: By clicking on the 'EDIT' button to edit all fields of a user's profile. Click 'UPDATE' save changes or 'CANCEL' to discard changes and return to the User Details page.
Enable/Disable a user	Use the green/red slider icon to set a user active or inactive. This prevents him or her from logging in until he or she is enabled.
Add new user to the organisation	By clicking the button 'ADD USER', you are directed to the add user page. Fill in the field. Click 'SAVE' to create the new user or click 'CANCEL' to discard changes and return.

ID	Email	Role	City	First name	Last name	Facility	Is hosting	Actions
9	cm1@childrescue.eu	Case Manager	-	Demo	Cm Soc	Επιψου Αούν		
15	alex22@childrescue.eu	Volunteer	-	Alex22	Mich			
20	nikolasgala.patra@gmail.com	Volunteer	-	Nikos	Galanos			
10	nm1@childrescue.eu	Network Manager	-	Demo	Nm Soc	Επιψου Αούν		
25	m.p.ariadni@gmail.com	Volunteer	-	Ariadni	Michalitsi			
17	atsirigoti@gmail.com	Volunteer	-	Antonia	Tsirigoti			
19	demerouth@gmail.com	Volunteer	-	Paraskivi	Demerouti			
22	ch.chasapi@gmail.com	Volunteer	-	Chrysoula	Chasapi			
23	efthimipapa144@gmail.com	Volunteer	-	Efthimia	Papakala			
28	kakarouba@gmail.com	Volunteer	-	Sia	Kakarouba			

Figure I-30 Organisation User Management

1.5.2.5 Children Registry (only applicable for Pilot on UMC)

Available for: Organisation Coordinator in Organisations with Hosting Facilities.

The “Children Registry” page contains all children that are either hosted by the organisation’s facilities or have been registered in the organisation but are not hosted. It can be used, therefore, as the main database for a tracing request or any other child-related query by RED CROSS in Greece. The children registry presents the following information for each child: First name, Last name, Status²(Figure I-31).

**The Hosting Facility Manager has "Search" only rights*

Table I-6 "Children Registry" Page Actions

What to do	How
View list with all children that have been registered or are hosted in the organisation’s hosting facilities.	It is the Default view. You can sort the values by clicking each header.
Search a specific child’s record	Use the Search field
View more information of a record	By clicking on the record’s row, you are directed to the “Child Record” (see more in Section I.5.3.1).

²The Status field of a child’s record can be “active” or “inactive”. By “active” meaning that the child has been reported missing and there is an active investigation around its case. By “inactive” meaning either that the child is safe and sound in the hosting facility, or it’s whereabouts are unknown but has not been declared as missing and there is no running investigation.

Figure I-31 Children Registry page

1.5.2.6 Hosted Children

Available for: Hosting Facility Manager

The Hosted Children page (Figure I-32) contains all children that are hosted in Hosting Facility of the specific HFM. The record preview includes a thumbnail photo, the full name of the child, missing-from date and a case status indicator.

What to do	How
View grid with the children hosted by the organisation’s hosting facility	It is the Default view. Use the ‘Sort by’ option to sort records by date (‘Recently Disappeared’ or ‘Recently Updated’).
Search a specific child’s record	Use the Search field
View more information of a record	By clicking on the record’s thumbnail, you are directed to the “Child Record” (see more in Section I.5.3.1)
Add new child record	By clicking on the ‘CREATE’ button you are directed to the create case page. Complete all required fields and other fields you have information for. Click ‘SAVE’ to create the new case or ‘CANCEL’ to discard changes and return.

Figure I-32 Hosted Children page

I.5.3 Case Management

Available for: Organisation Owner, Organisation Coordinator, Case Manager, Network Manager (view only), Hosting Facility Manager ('search' functionality)

The user can have a preview of all active cases and closed cases that have not been archived, which are under the jurisdiction of the organisation (Figure I-33). The user can also add new cases from this page (Figure I-34). The record preview includes a thumbnail photo, the full name of the child, missing-from date and a case status indicator.

* *the Network Manager has 'view-only' rights.* The Hosting Facility Manager can only use the 'search' functionality and

Table I-7 "Case Management" Page Actions

What to do	How
View grid of the organisation's cases	It is the Default view. Use the 'Sort by' option to sort cases by date ('Recently Disappeared' or 'Recently Updated'). Use the 'Filter by' option to view only active, closed, archived or all cases.
Search a specific case	Use the Smart Search functionality to check for existing records with similar sounding full names. Two-fold purpose: "tracing requests" inquiry and avoid duplicates.
View more information for a case	By clicking on the case's thumbnail, you are directed to the "Child Record" (see more in Section I.5.3.1).
Add new case	By clicking on the 'CREATE' button you are directed to the create case page. Complete all required fields and other fields you have information for. Click 'SAVE' to

create the new case or 'CANCEL' to discard changes and return.

Figure I-33 Case Management Page

Figure I-34 Add New Case

1.5.3.1 Child Record

Available for: Organisation Owner, Organisation Coordinator, Case Manager, Hosting Facility Manager, Network Manager

The user can find information about the child and the case, organised in tabs and perform various actions based on her user role.

1.5.3.2 "Case" Tab

* The Network Manager has 'view-only' rights for this tab.

Table I-8 "Case" Tab Actions

What to do	How
View the photo and some basic information - personal, demographics, physical - about the child	It is the Default view
Edit the case information	By clicking the button 'EDIT CASE', you are directed to a page where you can edit all the fields of the case record and upload a new photo. Click 'SAVE' to keep changes. Click the back arrow or 'CANCEL' to discard changes.
Close an active case	By clicking the button 'CLOSE CASE', the case is indicated as closed and all active alerts are deactivated.

Figure I-35 Case Tab

1.5.3.3 "Alerts" tab

The user can view all the alerts that have been created for the case. An alert includes the following information: Full Name, Custom Name (a shortcut of the child's name that has been defined for public use), Address (centre of the alert), Radius (defined alert radius), Description (free text accompanying the alert with more information), End (the date and time of alert expiration), Active (green while the alert is active).

* The Hosting Facility Manager and Network Manager have 'view-only' rights for this tab.

Table I-9 "Alerts" Tab Actions

What to do	How
View list with all alerts that have been created for the case	It is the Default view. You can sort the values by clicking each header. You can choose the number of alerts displayed per page.
View more information for an alert	By clicking anywhere on the row of the alert, a popup window shows, displaying the alert details and a map view of the area covered by the alert.
Deactivate an active alert	By clicking anywhere on the row of the alert, a popup window shows. Click on the 'DEACTIVATE' button to set the alert inactive.
Create new alert	By clicking on the 'CREATE ALERT' button, a popup window shows. Complete the required fields and configure the location and duration of the alert. Click 'SAVE' to activate the alert or 'CLOSE' to discard changes.

Figure I-36 Add new Alert

1.5.3.4 "Facts" tab

All feedback regarding a case is in the "Facts" tab. The user can view a list with some of the feedback's information and click on it to see more. A feedback includes the following information: Description (free text with more information), Address, Date of Incident, Media (if any - attached photo), Source (can be the mobile user who sent the feedback, or a manually added source by the web user), Checked By (the web user who checked the feedback), Status (pending, relevant, irrelevant, credible), Child Status (selection from list of options), Transportation (selection from list of options), Note (free text) .

* The Hosting Facility Manager and Network Manager have 'view-only' rights for this tab.

Table I-10 "Facts" Tab Actions

What to do	How
View list with all feedback for the case	It is the Default view. You can sort the values by clicking each header. You can choose the number of alerts displayed per page.
View more information for a specific feedback	By clicking anywhere on the row of the feedback, a popup window shows, displaying the alert details and a map view with the feedback location. Click the 'DOWNLOAD' button to download the alert locally as PDF file.
Edit specific feedback	Use the pencil icon to open the popup window and edit the Address, Status, Child Status, Transportation and Note fields of the feedback. Click 'SAVE' button to keep changes or 'CLOSE' to discard changes.
Create new feedback	By clicking on the 'PROVIDE FEEDBACK' button, a popup window shows. Complete the fields and click 'SAVE' to create the new feedback or 'CLOSE' to discard changes.

Figure I-37 Add new Fact

1.5.3.5 "Volunteers" Tab

The user can view a list of the organisation's Volunteers who have been invited to the case's collaboration space. The user can see basic information about the Volunteer and her involvement/role

in the case: First Name, Last Name, City, Team (search team for this case), is a Team Leader, Invitation status (Accepted, Pending) and registry number (only for RED CROSS volunteers, since they are already accredited as volunteers and registered with the Organisation holding a registry number).

Table I-11 "Volunteers" Tab Actions

What to do	How
View list of volunteers participating in the case	It is the Default view. You can sort the values by clicking each header.
Add volunteers to this case by Sending invitation with message	By clicking the button 'Invite volunteers', a list of all organisation volunteers appears and you select the appropriate members.
Search the list	Use the Search field
Set a volunteer as a team leader	Use the pencil icon to edit the volunteer and click the appropriate tick-box
Assign a name to each team	Use the pencil icon to edit the volunteer and fill in the field 'Team name'
Remove volunteer from case	Use the recycle bin icon

Figure I-38 Invite more Volunteers

1.5.3.6 "Files" Tab

The user can view documents that have been uploaded to the child’s record and download them. In the thumbnail preview you can see a preview of the document (if it is a photo), the user who uploaded it, the name of the file (Figure I-39).

Table I-12 "Files" Tab Actions

What to do	How
View uploaded files for the case	It is the Default view. It contains a grid with the thumbnail views of the uploaded documents.
Download an uploaded file	Use the download icon on the thumbnail of the document to store the file locally.
Delete an uploaded file	Use the recycle bin icon on the thumbnail of the document to remove the file from the record.
Upload new file	By clicking the button 'ADD FILE' you can upload a new file to the record from your local storage.

Figure I-39 Files Tab

1.5.3.7 "Places" Tab

The user can view a list of places associated to the case. These places are either directly registered by the web user or derived from the Feedbacks or the results of the Analytics. They include the following information: Address, Tag (selection from list of options), Source (selection from list of options), Description (free text) (Figure I-40).

Table I-13 "Places" Tab Actions

What to do	How
View list with all places of interest (POI) for the case	It is the Default view. You can sort the values by clicking each header. You can choose the number of POIs displayed per page.

View evaluation of POI resulted from data analysis	Related to spatiotemporal analysis. Updated frequently.
View Social Networks information (APIs)	A one-off retrieval of popular venues and events in the general area of disappearance
View more information for a specific POI	By clicking anywhere on the row of the POI, a popup window shows, displaying the POI details and a map view with the location.
Edit specific POI	Use the pencil icon to open the popup window and edit the fields of the POI. Click 'UPDATE PLACE' button to keep changes or 'CLOSE' to discard changes.
Delete specific POI	Use the delete icon to open the popup window. Click 'REMOVE' button to remove it from the places list or 'CANCEL' to return

Figure I-40 Add new Place

1.5.3.8 "Control" Tab

The user can use this tab to have an overview of the search operations' status and to communicate with other users who participate in the case. The Control Tab includes a map that can illustrate the active alerts, the addresses of feedback, POIs (the pinpoints of the Places), the location of Volunteers who have joined the operations. The map refreshes automatically every few seconds. The Places' Address, Tag and Source are also displayed in a list. The Volunteers' Name, Team and Role are enlisted in a second list. In the right column, the user can find the newsfeed area, with posts from all users participating in the collaboration space (Figure I-41).

Table I-14 "Control" Tab Actions

What to do	How
View a map with all locations related to the case	A map is available in the upper area of the Default view. You can tick the relevant option to display the alerts, facts, POIs and volunteers of the case on the map. Also view any geospatial information derived from data analytics (e.g. suggested radius for search).
View list with POIs of the case	A list with the Address, Tag and Source of every POI of the case is available in the left column of the Default view.
View list of Volunteers who participate in the case	A list with the Name, Team and Role of every volunteer who participates in the case is available in the middle column of the Default view.
View Newsfeed for the case	A list with all posts for the case is available in the right column of the Default view.
Create new post for the Newsfeed	By clicking on the 'CREATE POST' button, a popup window shows. Complete the fields and if you want to attach an image. Click 'UPLOAD' to share the post on the Newsfeed section or click 'CLOSE' to discard changes and return.

Figure I-41 Create new Post

1.5.3.9 "Analytics" Tab

Table I-15 "Analytics" Tab Actions

What to do	How
View data insights and statistics dashboard	It is the Default view. You can view the results of analytics for the case. You can choose Day/Week/Month preview.
Interact with analytics	Use the '+' '-' icons to zoom-in/out the whole diagram. Use the magnifying glass icon to zoom-in to a selected area of the diagram. With the hand icon you can drag the diagram.

Figure I-42 Analytics Page - Diagram 1

Figure I-43 Analytics Page - Diagram 2